

Oxygen partial pressure dependent tuning of Cu₂O & CuO thin films by Reactive RF Magnetron Sputtering.

Sai Guru Srinivasan S.,^a M.C.Santhosh Kumar^a

Opto electronic materials and devices lab, Department of Physics, National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli-620
015, India.

Corresponding author: santhoshmc@nitt.edu

Abstract:

Nanostructured Cu₂O & CuO thin films are deposited on glass substrates by radio frequency (RF) magnetron sputtering using a Cu metal target in an Ar and O₂ reactive atmosphere at 50W of RF power. The functions of oxygen partial pressure in the deposition of Cu₂O & CuO thin films were studied at fixed substrate temperature of 300°C. The structural, morphological, optical and electrical properties of the deposited thin films were investigated by using X-ray diffraction (XRD), field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), UV–Vis spectrophotometry and Hall effect measurement system. The XRD results shows that Cu₂O crystalline phase is obtained at 5% oxygen partial pressure and the phase changes to CuO on increasing the oxygen partial pressure above 10%. SEM images reveal that the deposited thin films are highly uniform. The optical band gaps of as-deposited Cu₂O and CuO samples are 2.18 eV and 1.83 eV respectively. The electrical conductivity of the films obtained using Hall measurement as $1.42 \times 10^{-1} (\Omega \cdot \text{cm})^{-1}$ for Cu₂O and $1.39 (\Omega \cdot \text{cm})^{-1}$ for CuO samples.

Keywords: Copper Oxide; Reactive RF sputtering; p-type semiconductor